

OCEAN:ICE News – October 2024

OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN:ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to October's edition of OCEAN:ICE News! We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN:ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, including the EPOC Annual Meeting 2024, OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting and IAPSO, JCI/OI, and SOOS Workshop, and our Climate Coffees. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming Ocean Best Practices System Workshop VIII and more exciting events.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in November!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Stina Wahlgren

We are continuing with our article series 'Researcher in the Spotlight'. Check out our latest feature on Stina Wahlgren, a physical oceanography PhD student at [University of Gothenburg](#).

Read the feature on Stina [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN:ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN:ICE Activities

OCEAN:ICE at EPOC Annual Meeting 2024

OCEAN:ICE took part in the [EPOC](#) annual meeting in Reading on 18-20th September 2024. [Andrew Meijers](#) presented on the progress and upcoming goals of OCEAN:ICE, and acted as part of the expert advisory group advising EPOC on its progress.

In turn Eleanor Frajka-Williams from EPOC attended the OCEAN:ICE annual project meeting in Copenhagen on the 24th of September 2024 to deliver an EPOC update and to discuss areas of overlap and complementary research, notably in modelling of the AMOC.

The Great Ocean Conveyor

This schematic was developed for **millennial timescales** but applying it to human timescales (days to 100 years) **leads to misconceptions:**

- that **convection** is synchronous with AMOC transport
- that the AMOC at **any latitude** characterises the AMOC at all latitudes

It glosses over processes and timescales which break coherence but which may dictate AMOC's role in climate.

Fig. 1: The great ocean conveyor logo (Broecker, 1987). (Illustration by Joe Le Monnier, Natural History Magazine.)

OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting and IAPSO, JCIOI, and SOOS Workshop

The OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting was held in conjunction with the International Association for the Physical Sciences of the Oceans (IAPSO) joint event, which took place at the [Danish Meteorological Institute](#) in Copenhagen and virtually via Zoom from September 23 to 25, 2024. The joint event included OCEAN:ICE's Annual Project Meeting (September 23–24) and a Joint OCEAN:ICE, [IAPSO, Joint Commission on Ice-Ocean Interactions](#) (JCIOI), and [Southern Ocean Observing System](#) (SOOS) Workshop, 'Reconciling Cross-Platform Observations of Ice-Shelf Melt (RECOIL),' on September 25. The collaborative event fostered knowledge sharing, partnership, and networking opportunities.

The event brought together Southern Ocean and cryosphere scientists from various projects, associations, commissions, including OCEAN:ICE, IAPSO, JCIOI, and SOOS, as well as researchers from other projects funded by the European Union and UK Research and Innovation. Participants included oceanographers, climate scientists, cryosphere researchers, modelers, data management experts, and outreach specialists, fostering a diverse and interdisciplinary dialogue. Collaborators from related projects within the [EU Polar Cluster](#) and beyond also attended, contributing to a rich exchange of expertise across multiple fields.

Figure 1 Participants of the OCEAN:ICE, IAPSO, JCIOI and SOOS Workshop

The OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting No. 2 (year 2024) showcased the extensive scientific progress made across all work packages, offering a platform for partners to present detailed results, discuss key achievements, and outline future goals. The meeting highlighted the substantial amount of research conducted over the past year, from advancements in subpolar circulation and ice-ocean interactions to significant insights into ice sheet mass balance and deep uncertainties in freshwater fluxes. Despite the impressive work already completed, the project still has time remaining, and discussions focused on refining the trajectory for the coming year, ensuring continued momentum. The meeting also fostered collaboration between work packages, setting the stage for further breakthroughs and reinforcing the commitment to fulfilling the project's long-term objectives.

Representatives from all participants and partners were invited to the OCEAN:ICE annual project meeting to participate either in person or virtually. Partners represented were the following: [DMI](#), [NORCE](#), [AWI](#), [CNRS](#), [UU](#), [ETT](#), [ULB](#), [ENS-LMD](#), [PIK](#), [UGOT](#), [NPI](#), [EPB](#), [NASC](#), [UKRI-BAS](#), [UNN](#), [UoS](#), [ULIVERPOOL](#), [UREAD](#). There were around 50 in-person and 10 virtual attendees at the OCEAN:ICE annual project meeting, and around 40 attending in-person and 5 virtually the joint workshop with IAPSO, JCIOI, and SOOS.

The proceedings of the OCEAN:ICE and IAPSO, JCIOI, and SOOS Workshop 'Reconciling Cross-Platform Observations of Ice-Shelf Melt (RECOIL)' are going to be made available in the OCEAN:ICE Zenodo community [Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System](#) as well as the OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting report.

Read more on the OCEAN:ICE [website](#).

Figure 2 Participants of the OCEAN:ICE Annual Project Meeting

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Ocean Best Practices System Workshop VIII

[ObsSea4Clim](#), [TipESM](#), [ClimTip](#) and [OCEAN:ICE](#) projects are jointly going to deliver the workshop 'Ocean-Climate Nexus – Importance of Ocean Observing for Tipping Points' on the 17th of October 2024, at 17:00-18:30 CEST. Andrew Meijers (BAS) will deliver a talk on Novel Ocean Observations representing OCEAN:ICE.

Join this free online workshop by registering [here](#).

Ocean best practices

2021 United Nations Ocean Decade
2030 Sustainable Development

OBPS Workshop VIII / 14-18 October, 2024 [ONLINE]
Ocean-Climate Nexus - Importance of Ocean Observing for Tipping Points, and the downstream effects of Tipping Points.
17 Oct | 15:00 - 16:30 UTC

Background images credits: Toby Matthews (Manta Ray) and Shann Wirth (Science Dive) / Ocean Image Bank

Climate Coffee

Ana Oliveira on CLIM4cities ML and AI Modelling

17 October 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Ana Oliveira

AI for Urban Climate: An EO-Based Approach for Heatwaves Exposure and Adaptation – CLIM4cities project

17 October 2024 | 10:00 - 10:40 CEST
Online

Danish Meteorological Institute

CLIM4cities is under a programme of, and funded by, the European Space Agency. Views expressed do not reflect the official opinion of the European Space Agency.

[Oliver Huhn](#) on [Record of Water Mass Age and Meltwater Fractions, Weddell Sea](#)

14 November 2024, 10:00 – 10:40 (CEST).

Register [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Oliver Huhn

Record of water mass age and meltwater fractions, Weddell Sea

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Danish Meteorological Institute

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Happening Soon

OCEAN:ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- **17 October 2024**, [Ocean Best Practices System Workshop VIII](#) 'Ocean-Climate Nexus – Importance of Ocean Observing for Tipping Points', online
- **21-23 October 2024**, [PolarRES](#) Annual Meeting, Potsdam
- **28-30 October 2024**, [SO-CHIC](#) Annual Project Meeting, Paris & online

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN:ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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Who is OCEAN:ICE?

OCEAN:ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN:ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN:ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN:ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

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